

State Safety as an Object of Legal Protection in Ukraine

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Abstract

The article is designed to determine the state of statutory regulation for preventing state safety violations. The methods of scientific cognition, both general and specialized, were used to achieve the defined aim, where the central place was occupied by dialectic and structural-logical methods, synthesis, and analysis. The study shows that the basis of the approach researchers in administrative and legal sciences advocate is the inextricable relationship between national security and defense. Furthermore, it is crucial to establish the content of state security to determine the nature of this approach. The effectiveness of the implemented military defense measures is equal to the extent of the country's defense capability. The study substantiates that the concept of defense in relation to state security is defined as the implementation of measures to prevent and repel an attack on the country's territory. The article concluded that defense should be interpreted within the substantive, competent, and organizational and legal approaches. The substantive approach defines defense as a set of certain military actions to overcome an internal conflict or an external attack. According to the competent approach, defense is a range of powers of authorities that must be exercised to ensure the defense capability of the state and certain territories (the territories of state borders, the coast of the territorial sea, and internal marine resources). The organizational and legal approach considers defense a set of normative provisions defining the rights and obligations of participants in defense legal relations, the object and subject of such a sphere of legal regulation. The state security functions are substantiated to be performed constantly and under martial law or in the absence of a military threat. These functions are associated with the adoption of comprehensive

measures to protect the state interests in areas of economy, social regulation, spiritual and cultural growth, environmental protection, etc.

Keywords: Ensuring human rights, state security, defense, competence, powers

1. Introduction

The study of the problems of prevention of crimes that encroach on state security is extremely multifaceted and complex, which is determined by a number of normative and scientific-theoretical factors. Within the framework of the disclosure of such scientific problems, it is necessary first of all to determine the content of the category “state security,” its essence, and the place it occupies in the system of objects of legal protection. The content of offenses against state security is established by examining the issues of organized crime prevention and observance of the proper level of law and order, which in general can be equivalently assessed as “serving the people.” Functionally, the measures to prevent offenses against state security should first and foremost protect the rights and interests of the people of Ukraine, as defined by the Constitution of Ukraine (Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine, 1996), which emphasizes that human security is the highest social value.

Thus, the understanding of the category “state security” requires its clarification through the understanding of the content of such regulatory and legal concepts as human security, personal security, national security, right of defense, right of sovereignty. A comprehensive unified approach to understanding the category state security has not yet been developed; in addition, the absence of a fixed understanding of its essence and content is determined at the normative level.

The authors of this research strive to define the content of the mentioned categorical series to develop an original approach to understanding the category “state security.” The measures for preventing offenses in this field are further outlined and subdivided according to their content. The statutory regulation for preventing violations of state security was an issue to research for both representatives of the military (Skulysh, 2012; Hrushko, 2021) and administrative sciences (Sokurenko, 2017; Averyanov, 2005).

Despite numerous studies in this field, some issues remained unsettled and, given the ongoing war, affected the implementation of law-making activities. The law enforcement activity and statutory regulation require rethinking, especially in the field of state security. The methods of scientific cognition, both general and specialized, were used in this study, where the central place was occupied by abstract-logical, deductive, inductive, historical, modeling and forecasting, methods of system-structural, system and functional analysis. The use of system analysis methods made it possible to determine the state of statutory regulation for preventing violations of state safety. This article puts forward the aim to determine the state of statutory regulation for preventing violations of state safety in Ukraine and justify the suggested amendments to the legislation of Ukraine in the corresponding field.

2. The Relationship of the Categories “Defense” and “State Safety”

Article 1 of the Law of Ukraine “On the National Security of Ukraine” (Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine, 2018) defines state security as “the protection of state sovereignty, its territorial integrity, the constitutionally established democratic system, and any vital national interests from real and potential non-military threats.” Thus, the understanding of the category “state security” requires its clarification through the understanding of the content of such regulatory and legal concepts as “human security”, “personal security”, “national security”, “right of defense”, “right of sovereignty”. A comprehensive unified approach to understanding the category “state security” has not yet been developed; in addition, the absence of a fixed understanding of its essence and content is determined at the normative level.

In scientific publications, the concept of "defense" is investigated using a number of methodological approaches. The first approach developed in the publications of representatives of administrative and legal science is the understanding of defense as the adoption of a certain set of organizational, economic, and political measures by state authorities to guarantee the preservation of the integrity of the state territories, which must be used under the conditions of a special regime - martial law (Bytyaka, 2007; Averyanov, 2005). At the same time, V.V. Sokurenko (2017) emphasizes the expediency of a common interrelated understanding of such concepts as national security, military security, defense, without distinguishing the category of state security.

The researchers interpret the provision of national and military security as the requirements that should be met to ensure the integrity of the country's territory and guarantee state sovereignty. Therefore, the basis of the approach researchers in administrative and legal sciences advocate is the inextricable relationship between national security and defense. However, the issue of establishing the content of state security is not investigated separately. Thus, under such an approach, effectiveness of the implemented military defense measures is equal to the extent of the country's defense capability. Within the scope of research by representatives of military science, the concept of defense in relation to state security is defined as the implementation of measures to prevent and repel an attack on the country's territory. An interesting conclusion reached in the studies of I.I. Hrushko (2021) regarding the understanding of national defense needs as a circle of state security interests.

In the studies of V.P. Shkidchenko and V.D. Kochno (2000) determined that the criteria for the commensurability of the concepts "military security" and "defense" is the understanding of the latter through the state's ability to deflect and repel external military aggression by armed means, while the first concept is defined by scientists as the ability to respond to negative domestic threats to the country's integrity. Provision of military security functions, according to V.P. Shkidchenko and V.D. Kohno (2000), is considered as taking a set of measures not only in the field of defense capability, but also in matters of internal and external policy, economic security and the economic capacity of the state to meet the needs of the population in the conditions of a declared armed attack or in the conditions of martial law. The opposite approach is advocated in the study of O.I. Pogibko (2009), where the sphere of military security refers to the components of defense, and is separated from national security. As noted by V.Y. Pashynsky (2017), the legislative understanding of national security is primarily based on the performance of the defense function of the state, which significantly narrows its essence.

Determining the content of the category "state security" as the basis of this article, it is necessary to focus on the provisions of Article 17 of the Constitution of Ukraine (Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine, 1996). The Article stipulates that "the first and foremost function of the state and Ukrainian people shall be defined as the protection of Ukraine's sovereignty and territorial integrity, as well as guaranteeing its economic and information security. The Armed Forces of Ukraine are entrusted to defend Ukraine and protect its sovereignty, territorial integrity, and inviolability." Therefore, the understanding of defense is connected with the preparation and, if necessary, the activation of an established mechanism of interrelated complex measures, means, tools capable of performing the function of protecting the territorial integrity of the state, which is required in the event of an armed attack on the state (Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine, 2020), which must differ from the understanding categories "state security" and "national security".

The decision of the NSDC, signed by the President of Ukraine on 25th of March, 2021, establishes that the military security of Ukraine is one of the grounds for exercising the right to self-determination by the people of Ukraine. This Decree No. 121/2021 also establishes the grounds for reaffirming the state of Ukraine and guaranteeing its sustainable development

guided by the rule of law and based on the highest values of democracy, dignity, security, freedom, and prosperity of citizens (President of Ukraine, 2021).

The Military Security Strategy of Ukraine as of 2023 recognized the escalation of armed aggression by the Russian Federation as one of the identified threats to the state of Ukraine. This threat is not limited to one country but involves potential armed aggression by other states or coalitions. This military force against Ukraine has a full-scale nature and implies military operations with decisive actions, psychological pressure, cyber attacks, information campaigns, and the blockade of airspace, seaports, etc. Based on such a normative provision, military security and defense must differ from state security in that its violation is associated with the commission of armed aggression both by foreign states and within the limits of internal local conflicts, including those of religious origin. In particular, the above-mentioned normative legal act included "provoked and externally supported armed conflict within the territory of Ukraine, which may be accompanied by the massive use of armed violence, illegal armed formations (private military campaigns), international, inter-confessional or social - political instability" (President of Ukraine, 2021).

The understanding of the category "defense" is excellent within military science, administrative and legal science, as well as within the science of public management and administration. For representatives of military science, it is characteristic to understand "defense" as certain actions of a combat nature, which are implemented in order to overcome the manifestations of an offensive, an invasion, which is often carried out with the advantage of forces and weapons, which requires compliance with the principles of saving human and property resources, and is aimed at achieving the defeat of the enemy (Polyakov et al., 2014). Therefore, the content of defense within the limits of military science consists in taking measures aimed directly at defeating the enemy.

Within the framework of administrative and legal science, a slightly different approach to understanding the category of "defense" is defined, the generally recognized approach is used, that its content consists in taking a complex of interrelated, but at the same time multifaceted measures in various spheres of social life (in the sphere of economics, politics, information influence, military equipment, etc.), the necessity of which is determined by the requirements of repelling an armed attack, both internal and external, including the use of the Armed Forces of Ukraine, as well as taking countermeasures as a component of international obligations (President of Ukraine, 2021). V.V. Sokurenko (2017) determines the necessary use of a combination of organizational, economic, social, legal, scientific and technical and other measures for the effectiveness of defense.

Thus, within the limits of administrative and legal science, there is an understanding of the concept of defense as a set of organizational, economic, social, legal, scientific and technical measures, which together can ensure the effectiveness of repelling an external or internal attack or invasion.

The administrative aspect of understanding the defense of the state safety in considering the content of the competence of state authorities and local self-government bodies, special military administration bodies that can be created to ensure the defense capability of the area under martial law conditions (Bogdanovych et al., 2012). At the same time, there should be a high formalization of implementation processes of the public administration function, taking place under conditions of inadmissibility of discretion by powerful subjects.

So, summarizing the carried out scientific study of the content of the "defense" category in its relationship with the "state security" category, the following conclusion is admissible. Defense is understood through the prism of the following scientific approaches:

- substantive - as a set of certain military actions aimed at overcoming an internal conflict or an external attack;

- competent - as a range of powers of authorities, which must be implemented in order to ensure the defense capability of the state and certain territories (in particular, the territory of state borders, the coast of the territorial sea and internal marine resources);
- organizational and legal - as a complex of normative provisions defining the rights and obligations of participants in defense legal relations, the object and subject of such a sphere of legal regulation.

Whereas the state security functions are performed constantly and under martial law or in the absence of a military threat. These functions are associated with the adoption of comprehensive measures to protect the state interests in areas of economy, social regulation, spiritual and cultural growth, environmental protection, etc. In this sense, it is worth supporting the approach of V.Y. Pashynsky (2017), which defines the category of "defense" as a set of legal relations arising in the socio-political sphere, socio-economic, scientific-technical, informational, and aimed at overcoming manifestations of armed aggression - external or internal. So, summarizing, it is necessary to emphasize that the defense function is a separate function of the state, the purpose of which is to ensure the territorial integrity of the state, the protection of state and people's sovereignty from armed external or internal attack. The effective performance of the state's defense function depends on the proper compliance with state security requirements as a component of Ukraine's national security by the administrative apparatus.

The effectiveness of the functioning of the administrative-legal mechanism for ensuring compliance with state security requirements is directly related to the ability to prevent offenses in the researched area, which is a component of the competence of state law enforcement agencies in particular. The problem of normative and legal regulation of the competence of law enforcement agencies, the presence of constant processes of their reform in general, and in particular, in the field of defense, definitely affects the quality of overcoming illegal manifestations in the field of state security of Ukraine. Taking into account the conclusion reached above, that ensuring the requirements of state security is a set of measures to influence the development of society, which should be characterized by complexity, then its unconditional component is the creation of an appropriate administrative and legal basis for the prevention of offenses (Pashynsky, 2017). Thus, the administrative-legal norms contained in the military-administrative acts perform a regulatory function in the sphere of ensuring state security requirements. These norms are aimed at streamlining, organizing and improving social relations arising in the field of public management of state defense.

The main tasks of such norms include: regulation of the activities of military institutions and units in order to establish the order of formation, functioning, instructions and requirements for military units, as well as the rules of their activity; ensuring internal order, which consists in regulating discipline, subordination, military training, military service, keeping military records, etc.; control over compliance with legality, which consists in establishing procedures and mechanisms for control over compliance with legality in the sphere of state security; protection of the rights and interests of servicemen, which is manifested in the creation of a system of guarantees of the rights and interests of servicemen, determining the procedure for providing servicemen with housing, medical assistance, social security, etc.; regulation of military-civilian relations, the subject of which is determining the order of cooperation between military and civilian organizations in the field of defense and state security. Consequently, these norms play an important role in ensuring the efficiency and functioning of the state security system, contributing to the creation of a military legal order and providing the necessary organizational base for the implementation of defense activities.

Thus, the legal regulation of public relations in the sphere of state safety is implemented within the provisions of administrative law, where the issues of administrative responsibility, administrative procedures and administrative control, in particular, are fixed.

3. Administrative-Legal Regulation and Administrative-Legal Support of State Safety

It is important to implement the ratio of administrative-legal regulation and administrative-legal support of activities in the field of prevention of offenses related to non-compliance with state security requirements. The issue of administrative-legal provision of this or that sphere of public life, including compliance with state security requirements, is implemented through the creation of an appropriate normative-legal or administrative basis for the regulation of such relations, and therefore administrative-legal regulation is an element of the administrative-legal mechanism. Implementation of law-making activities in the sphere of ensuring state security requirements, as noted by V.Y. Pashynsky (2017), it must first of all be determined by the limits of the competence of powerful subjects, where the Security Service of Ukraine occupies an important place. It is permissible to conclude that the administrative and legal provision of state security is a complex of law-making and law-implementing means of influence on issues of maintaining the integrity of borders, creating conditions for repelling an attack and taking countermeasures, which are determined by the scope of competence of the authorities.

Continuing to clarify the content of the research methodology for the prevention of offenses against state security requires establishing its relationship with the category "national security". Article 1 of the Law of Ukraine "On the National Security of Ukraine" (Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine, 2018) defines national security as "the protection of state sovereignty, its territorial integrity, the constitutionally established democratic system, and any national interests of Ukraine from existing and possible threats." Meanwhile, the provisions of the Law of Ukraine "On the National Security of Ukraine" stipulate that state security is "the protection of state sovereignty, its territorial integrity, the constitutionally established democratic system, and other vital national interests from real and potential non-military threats."

Therefore, the provision of the needs and requirements of state security requires compliance with systematic and complex approaches, which allows us to conclude that state security is a component of the national security system, which consists in overcoming negative influences that can be perpetrated on national interests protected by law, and that is not associated with an armed attack. In the system of national security law, it is necessary to distinguish such sub-branches of legal regulation as defense law (or military law), military-administrative law, state security law, where the latter includes such institutions of legal regulation as the institute of public (civilian) security, the institute of security air space, the Institute of Economic Security, the Institute of Environmental Security, the Institute of Information Security, the Institute of Maritime Security, etc.

The law of state security can also be divided into such constituent elements as the law of defense (or military law), and military-administrative law as a law related to ensuring the requirements of the territorial integrity of the state, which is used in normal conditions, in the absence of an armed external attack or in the absence of internal armed conflicts. The analysis of such approaches indicates the need to address the definition of the content of national interests and their relationship with public interests, state interests, interests of social groups, and personal interests. Understanding the content of state security and the system of state interests should be based on the understanding of the content of the interest protected by law, which is formed in international and European practices. The approach to understanding interest as a certain need and directions for its satisfaction is quite common (Venediktova, 2011). Interest can be considered as actions of the subject aimed at satisfying his needs (Zamorska, 2015). Interests are the social basis for the formation of law and its normative provisions. Law is formed based on the definition of the system of society's values, which are subject to normalization and require the search for effective ways of their protection. Everything that becomes a rule of law essentially has value for society and requires the search for means and guarantees to ensure its protection and proper implementation (Bogutsky, 2020).

The given approaches to the classification of the realization of interest as a social category, allow us to single out the system of forms of its provision and guarantee, among which we can distinguish: law-making, law-enforcing, law-enforcing (law enforcement) and justice. An important component of law enforcement has been determined by scientists to be the provision by the state of preventing or preventing the commission of offenses, which consists in the implementation of measures of state control and supervision, the prevention of tortious forms of activity of subjects, the proper functioning of the system of execution of punishment and administrative sanctions (Gerasymenko et al., 2022).

The conclusion reached in the works of A. Kubko (2007), which established the inexpediency of equating state interests with the interests of public officials and local self-government, is well-founded. Understanding of state interests by scientists occurs through the use of synergistic connections with the definition of the system of social needs and narratives. Social interests, acquiring the nature of state interests, pass the stage of their legalization, conditionally speaking. The system of state interests, according to A. Kubko (2007), is proclaimed in the Constitution of Ukraine first of all, and consists of the priority of the protection of state sovereignty, observance of the territorial integrity of the state, prevention of encroachments on the principles of state security and constitutional order, establishment of international cooperation on security issues, implementation and harmonization of current national legislation in accordance with the standards of the European Union, ensuring the effectiveness of crime prevention.

In order to objectify and subjectify state interests, it is necessary to study the historical and political features of the state formation, examine the functions of state institutions and the direction of their activities, and determine the ruling political and legal regime. Furthermore, the level of international cooperation of a country and its ties with the world community should also be considered. The system of state interests is developed under the impact of the following subjective factors: the degree of citizens' legal awareness, the psychological perception of law and state as a value, the ideology of particular influential groups, etc.

Attempts to normatively define the category "interest" are carried out within the framework of judicial practice and law-making practice. One of the first examples of the implementation of a law enforcement search to determine the content of the category "interest protected by law" was carried out within the framework of the decision of the Constitutional Court of Ukraine when deciding case No. 3-пн/99 of April 8, 1999, it was substantiated that the understanding of the categories "state interests" and "interests of the state" should be identified. The Constitutional Court of Ukraine substantiated the understanding of state interests as enshrined in the norms of current legislation (in particular, the Constitution of Ukraine) of the need "to implement state-wide (political, economic, social and other) actions, programs aimed at protecting the sovereignty, territorial integrity, state border of Ukraine, guaranteeing its state, economic, informational, ecological security, protection of land as national wealth, protection of the rights of all subjects of ownership and management, etc." The above-mentioned conclusion of the Constitutional Court of Ukraine confirmed the evaluative nature of the "state interest" category. At the same time, the establishment of the presence or absence in a certain case is entrusted to the subject of authority, empowered to resolve specific factual or legal circumstances, that is, it is within the procedural discretion of the state authority (in particular, in the analyzed case, such a subject was the prosecutor's office) (Constitutional Court of Ukraine, 1999).

The category "national interest" is in theoretical and practical relations with the category "state interest", which together form the basis for establishing the normative content of the category "state security". The provisions of the Law of Ukraine "On National Security" define the national interests of Ukraine as "the vital interests of a person, society and the state that

shall be fulfilled and thereby ensure the sovereignty of Ukraine, its progressive democratic development, as well as safe and decent living conditions for its citizens.”

An attempt to interpret such a legislative definition was made in a number of scientific publications. I.V. Panteleychuk (2012) determines that the content of the category "national interest" should be established through an understanding of the system of values of society and humanity, which are the goals of state development. Despite changes in state development strategies, rethinking of its goals and functions, national interests are a certain reference point for the ongoing social and political transformations.

4. The Concept of State Safety According to EU and American Law Science

Within the research of representatives of EU law science, there is a certain tendency to identify national and state interests (Hama, 2021; Behnke, 2006). R. Niebuhr (2013), a representative of the American school of international law and relations, was one of the first in scientific publications to use the term "national interest" in his own research. Scientists have substantiated that the idea of national interests follows from the recognition of the national values of society and the moral principles of regulating social relations, where the concept of justice is defined as the basis for establishing its essence. Therefore, the formation of state interests must comply with the principles of morality and justice, commonwealth and international cooperation, as noted by R. Niebuhr (2013). The scientist defined the author's approach to establishing the content of the national interest as the values of the state and its ideology, which must correspond to the moral principles of society, which is defined as a priority for the development of the mechanism for ensuring human rights and freedoms.

The idea of establishing the content of national interests through the definition of a system of universal human values is supported in the studies of R. Aron, D. Mahoney and B. Anderson (2017), which based the establishment of state functions on the idea of national unity. Scientists consider the concept of "state security" as a set of measures, means, methods of ensuring the ideas and principles of national unity. Within the framework of research carried out by representatives of political science, the idea is advocated along with the use of the concept of "national interest" to use the concept of "power of the nation", which is supposed to establish criteria for the effectiveness of state security. National interests should be considered from the point of view of determining the content of government policy and assessed for compliance with the moral principles of society (Kennan, 2014).

The need to objectify national interests is emphasized in the studies of J. B. Duroselle (1981). The idea of objectification was favorably evaluated in the studies of A. Wendt (1999) and defined as a certain normative imperative. Scholars of national interests substantiated the complexity of the category "national interest", which should be aimed at ensuring the integrity of the state, its independence, economic development and stability, social balance and equilibrium. This approach is not clearly evaluated by other scientists. Objections to the objectification of the category of national interests are expressed in the publications of J. Rosenau (1980), because the definition of values should always be considered as a certain evaluation process, and therefore depends on the subjective views of the authorized person. So, summarizing the above approaches to understanding the category of national interests, it should be noted that the basis of their understanding is the idea of social value and benefit. It is the values of society that influence the formation of the nation and are the basis for ensuring the requirements of state security.

The principles of implementation and protection of national and state interests are determined at the level of international legal acts. According to Art. 4(3) of the Treaty on the Establishment of the European Community (EU) and Art. 1(1), it is established that the realization of state interests must be limited by the interests of other states, which does not exclude the idea of globalization and international cooperation. This postulate is reflected in

the establishment of the principle of subsidiary policy in accordance with Art. 5(3) TEU (Consolidated European act of the Treaty, 1986). The idea of subsidiarity was first reflected in the Single European Act in 1986, which was devoted to issues of environmental protection; with the development of European legislation, the idea of subsidiarity was extended to other spheres of public life and regulatory regulation (Consolidated European act of the Treaty, 1986).

5. Conclusion

So, national interest is a concept that determines the interests and well-being of the country or state itself. This may include the security and defense of the country, economic development, diplomatic relations, cultural values, territorial integrity and other aspects that are considered important for the independence and prosperity of the state. The national interest is determined by state leaders and the government based on the country's needs and requirements, as well as taking into account its history, geography, economy, culture, and other factors. It can change from time to time depending on external conditions, threats and opportunities that the state faces. For many states, the protection of the national interest is one of the main goals of foreign and domestic policy. This may include the protection of territorial integrity, ensuring security and defense against external threats, economic development, raising the standard of living of citizens, ensuring social justice, etc. In general, national interest is a key concept in politics and international relations, as it determines the main directions and priorities of the state's activities in the international and domestic arena.

National interests can be manifested in various forms at the domestic and international levels. Here are some typical forms of manifestation of national interests: state interests (state security and military defense, which consists in ensuring the security and defense of the state against external threats under conditions of attack and outside such conditions); cyber security (protection of the country from cyber attacks and cyber espionage); security of energy supply (ensuring the stability and security of energy resources); economic interests (economic development: accelerating economic growth and raising the standard of living of citizens; foreign economic activity: developing international trade relations and attracting foreign investments; financial stability: preserving the stability of the financial system and the national currency); political interests (protection of sovereignty and guarantee of the country's independence from external interference; diplomatic relations: support and development of international relations to protect national interests; development of international influence: creation of partnerships and alliances for joint achievement of strategic goals); social interests (social justice: ensuring equal opportunities for all citizens and the fight against poverty; health care: developing the health care system and providing access to medical care; education: increasing the level of education and professional development of the population); cultural interests (preserving cultural heritage: protection and promotion of cultural values and traditions; language policy: language protection and development of language policy to support national identity); environmental interests (environmental protection: ensuring ecological sustainability and conservation of natural resources; combating climate change: developing and implementing strategies to reduce the impact of climate change); territorial interests (protection of territorial integrity: struggle for recognition of territorial claims by the international community; border management: ensuring border security and control over migration processes).

These forms of manifestation of national interests often interact with each other and determine the strategy of the country's actions in various spheres of its activity. Realization of these interests requires the government to develop and implement appropriate policies and measures that would help achieve national strategic objectives and strengthen state independence and prosperity. Thus, the state interests include but are not limited to the

following areas: statehood defense; maintenance of territorial integrity; protection of the state sovereignty; adherence to environmental safety requirements; ensuring the interaction between society and authority; maintenance of economic stability and well-being of citizens.

Considering state security through the prism of legal protection, the fourth paragraph of Article 1 of the Law of Ukraine “On National Security” should be amended as follows: “State security is a state of social development that provides for the satisfaction of national interests (statehood defense, maintenance of territorial integrity, protection of the state sovereignty, adherence to environmental safety requirements, ensuring the interaction between society and authority, maintenance of economic stability and well-being of citizens) by preventing external and internal threats, terrorist, intelligence, or any other encroachments by foreign state special services.

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